

Chemistry of Bis-2'-Cyanoethyl Derivatives of some Aromatic Amines: Part. IV*. Some Reactions of 2-Methyl-4-NN-bis-2'-Cyanoethyl-amino benzaldehyde

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The preparation and some reactions of 2-Methyl-4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino benzaldehyde were reported earlier¹. In this communication is embodied the observations made during the condensation of the aldehyde with cyanacetamide, rhodanine, nitromethane, isonicotinic hydrazide, hydantoin, thiohydantoin and some acyl glycines. Benzoyl, cinnomoyl, *o*- and *p*-chloro benzoyl, *m*-, and *p*-nitro benzoyl glycine and 3:5-dinitrobenzoyl glycine were chosen for this purpose.

The reason for studying these reactions and identifying the products is the usefulness of similar products obtained from NN-dimethyl aminobenzaldehyde (DAB). Rhodanine derivative of DAB has been found to be a good reagent for detecting copper, silver and mercury². Similarly the 5(4) oxazolones of DAB and Dimethyl-amino-cinnamaldehyde are highly coloured compounds and due to this property the aldehydes are found useful as reagents for the detection of naturally occurring acyl glycines by paper chromatography³. The nitromethane derivatives of aldehydes on reduction yield the corresponding amines which have found use as starting materials in the synthesis of chemotherapeutic agents⁴. The hydantoin derivatives of DAB and other tertiary amino benzaldehydes are reported to have hypoglycemic activity⁵. Because of these observations reported by earlier workers, it was thought that the derivatives of 2-Methyl-4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl amino benzaldehyde may also prove useful as the aldehyde bears a good deal of structural resemblance to DAB. The results obtained in preliminary experiments are very encouraging and the practical applications of the condensation products are under further systematic investigation and the results will be reported soon.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Methyl-4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino benzaldehyde was prepared by the method recommended by Abraham Thomas and P. I. Ittyerah¹ using dimethyl formamide as the formylating agent. The aldehyde melted at 148° and the yield was 64%.

*Part III. *This Journal*. 1963, **45**, 232.

1. Abraham Thomas and P. I. Ittyerah, *This Journal*, 1964, **41**, 38.
2. 'Organic Analytical Reagents' by Frank J. Welcher, Vol III, p-417; D. Van Nostrand Company, Inc., New York.
3. R. M. Acheson, D. A. Booth, R. Brettle and A. M. Harris, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3457.
4. J. R. Merchant and S. P. Agrawal, *This Journal*, 1963, **40**, 472.
5. S. S. Tewari and A. Swaroop, *This Journal*, 1963, **40**, 698.

2-Methyl-4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino benzoic acid was obtained by oxidising the aldehyde (1 g.) in presence of potassium permanganate solution (4 g. in 50 ml.). After passing sulphur dioxide, a white product was obtained which was dissolved in an aqueous solution of sodium bicarbonate, filtered and precipitated by the addition of dil. HCl. It was recrystallised from dilute ethanol forming shining needles melting at 206° with slight decomposition. Yield, 0.2 g. (19.5%). Found: N, 16.12%; $C_{14}H_{15}N_3O_2$ requires N, 16.34%.

2-Methyl-4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene cyanoacetamide separated as a pale yellow crystalline product by heating a mixture of the aldehyde (1.2 g.) and cyanoacetamide (0.42 g.) in an oil bath kept at 140°-145° for 4 hrs. The crude product was repeatedly washed with hot absolute alcohol. It melted at 254°(d). Yield, 1.4 g. (90.9%). Found: N, 22.64%; $C_{17}H_{17}N_5O$ requires N, 22.8%.

2-Methyl-4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene rhodanine was prepared by gently refluxing a mixture of the aldehyde (1.2 g.), rhodanine (0.67 g.) and glacial acetic acid (5 ml) for 2 hrs. The brick red solid which separated on cooling, was purified by recrystallisation from acetone. It melted at 264°. Yield, 0.9 g. (50.6%). Found: N, 15.72%; S, 17.32%; $C_{17}H_{16}N_4OS_2$ requires N, 15.98%; S, 17.98.

2-Methyl-4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-β-nitro-styrene separated as a dark red crystalline product by refluxing a mixture of the aldehyde (1 g), nitro-methane (1 ml), ammonium acetate (0.4 g.) and glacial acetic acid for 4 hrs. in an oil bath maintained at 130°-135°. The crude product was purified by recrystallisation from glacial acetic acid; m.p. 158°; yield, 0.85 g (68%). Found: N, 19.96%; $C_{15}H_{16}N_4O_2$ requires N, 19.72%.

Iso-nicotinic acid hydrazone of 2-methyl-4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino benzaldehyde was obtained by refluxing a mixture of the aldehyde (0.6 g), isoniazid (0.32 g.) and ethanol (20 cc.) for 2 hrs. The crude product was recrystallised from absolute alcohol forming white flakes, m.p. 216°; yield, 0.58 g. (66.7%). Found: N, 23.41%; $C_{20}H_{20}N_6O$ requires N, 23.23%.

2-Methyl-4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene hydantoin was prepared by refluxing a mixture of the aldehyde (1.2 g.), hydantoin (0.5 g.), ammonium acetate (0.4 g.), glacial acid (2 ml.) and dry benzene, for 20 ml. 3 hrs. in a 50 ml. round bottomed flask carrying a Dean-Stark constant water remover. The yellow solid obtained was repeatedly washed with hot ethanol. It melted at 265°. Yield, 1.3 g. (81.2%). Found: N, 21.08%; $C_{17}H_{17}N_5O_2$ requires N, 21.67%.

2-Methyl-4-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino benzylidene thiohydantoin was obtained by refluxing a mixture of the aldehyde (1.2 g.), thiohydantoin (0.58 g.), fused sodium acetate (0.5 g.), glacial acetic acid (2.5 ml.) and two drops of acetic anhydride, for 4 hrs. in an oil bath maintained at 155°-160°. It was recrystallised from methyl alcohol; m.p. 246°; yield; 1.05 g. (61.8%). Found: N, 20.21%; S, 9.18%; $C_{17}H_{17}N_5SO$ requires N, 20.65%; S, 9.45%. 5(4) Oxazolones were obtained by condensing the aldehyde with different acyl glycines. The analytical results, m.p. etc. of these oxazolones are given in the table I.

The following experiment illustrates the method adopted for the preparation of the oxazolones: A mixture of the aldehyde (1.2 g.), hippuric acid (1.0 g.) fused sodium

acetate (0.42g.) and acetic anhydride (2 ml.) was refluxed on a water bath for 2 hrs. The reddish orange solid obtained, was recrystallised from acetone or ethyl acetate, forming orange needles of 2-phenyl-4-(2'-methyl-4'-NN-bis-2"-cyanoethyl amino benzylidene)-5-oxazolone; m.p. 189°, yield 1.1 g (57.9%).

TABLE I

S. No.	Name	Formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen%	
					Found	Required
1.	2-Phenyl-4-R	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂	189	57.9	13.82	14.25
2.	2-Styryl-4-R	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂	224	55.0	13.61	13.66
3.	2-(<i>o</i> -Chloro Phenyl)-4-R	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	182	33.65	13.15	13.38
4.	2-(<i>p</i> -Chloro Phenyl)-4-R	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	246	40.4	13.34	13.38
5.	2-(<i>o</i> -Nitro Phenyl)-4-R	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄	240	44.67	16.20	16.32
6.	2-(<i>m</i> -Nitro Phenyl)-4-R	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄	269	33.7	16.23	16.32
7.	2-(<i>p</i> -Nitro Phenyl)-4-R	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄	289	56.07	16.17	16.32
8.	2-(3;5-Dinitrophenyl)-4-R	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₆	266	80.2	17.48	17.72

R stands for (2'-Methyl-4'-NN-bis-2"-cyanoethyl aminobenzylidene)-5-oxazolone.

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